

ENTREPRENEURSHIP CURRICULUM DELIVERY AND SECURITY CHALLENGES IN TECHNICAL COLLEGES IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract

This work examines entrepreneurship curriculum delivery and security challenges in Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Two specific objectives, two research questions and two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population for the study was 27 respondents comprising 9 vice principals academic and 18 entrepreneurship teachers. The sample size for the study was determined using a census sampling technique. A structured questionnaire entitled, "Entrepreneurship Curriculum Delivery in Security Challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State Questionnaire" (ECDSCTCQ) was used for data collection. The validation was done by an expert in entrepreneurship education, University of Uyo, while reliability was established using trial testing method on three (3) entrepreneurship education teachers in Federal Government Girls' Technical College, Uyo. The scores were analysed using Coefficient alpha and a coefficient of 0.98 was obtained. Independent t-test was used to analyse the data, and the result indicates that experiential learning and mentoring as instructional medium can influence entrepreneurship curriculum delivery and security challenges in technical colleges in Akwa Ibom State. It was recommended, among others, that teachers should be adequately trained through seminars and conferences on how entrepreneurship teaching and effective use of experiential and mentoring methods predict delivery of entrepreneurship curriculum and security challenges in technical colleges.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Curriculum Delivery, Security Challenges and Technical Colleges

Introduction

Education today is no doubt oriented towards the "take-a-job" mentality. It conveys in both content and attitude that the student is being prepared for a career in which he or she will be working for some kind of small or large business entity, i.e., "taking a job" that someone else has already created. The channelling of our nation's youth into the "employed-by-somebody-else" marketplace is particularly damaging. Entrepreneurship in education, therefore, significantly indicates that students should be encouraged to start up their own company - this is not about starting new organizations, but is about making students being more creative, opportunity oriented, proactive and innovative. This is at the core of entrepreneurship and is also a competence that all citizens need to have in today's society, regardless of career choice. Students can become highly motivated and engaged by creating value to other people based on the knowledge they acquire, and this can fuel deep learning and illustrate the practical relevance of the knowledge in question (Mahieu, 2016).

Curriculum refers to what a learner is required to encounter, study, practice and master. It entails taking decisions about what should be taught, how it should be taught and when it should be taught. The four (4) core elements of the curriculum are teaching, learning, assessment, and resources used for teaching and learning. Entrepreneurial curriculum contains information on how students can identify and shape opportunities, assess business concepts, develop operational plans, fund and launch ventures and grow new enterprises. Furthermore, it is about case studies which should be discussed in the classroom so as to provide students with another avenue for examining entrepreneurial strategies and learning about the successes and failures of new ventures (Kourilsky, 2015; OECD, 2010).

Stevenson and Jarillo (2010) define entrepreneurship as "a process by which individuals - either on their own or inside organizations - pursue opportunities without regard to the resources they currently control". Bruyat and Julien (2018) used a constructivist approach and propose a definition incorporating not only the entrepreneur, but also the new value created, the environment within which it takes place, the entrepreneurial process itself and the links between these constructs over time. They also proposed the terms "individual" and "entrepreneur" to represent teams whenever applicable. It encourages creative thinking and promotes a strong sense of self-worth, initiative and a tolerance to failure. It does not only give people the means to cope with an increasingly complex and uncertain world, but also gives them the mind-set and capabilities to thrive in it (Gibb, 2015).

According to O'Connor (2013), entrepreneurial education is often categorized into three approaches: teaching “about” entrepreneurship which means a content-laden and theoretical approach aimed at giving a general understanding of the phenomenon. It is the most common approach in higher education institutions (Mwasalwiba, 2010); teaching “for” entrepreneurship means an occupationally oriented approach aiming at giving budding entrepreneurs the requisite knowledge and skills. Teaching “through” on the other hand, has to do with a process based and often experiential approach where students go through an actual entrepreneurial learning process (Kyrö, 2019). This approach often leans on the wider definition of entrepreneurship, and can be integrated into other subjects in general education by connecting entrepreneurial characteristics, processes and experiences to the core subject. While the “about” and “for” approaches are relevant primarily to a subset of students at the secondary and tertiary levels of education, the embedded approach of teaching “through” entrepreneurship can be relevant to all students and at all levels of education (Handscombe et al., 2008). It is worthy of note that entrepreneurial education is also frequently seen as a response to the increasingly globalized, uncertain and complex world we live in, requiring all people and organizations in society to be increasingly equipped with entrepreneurial competencies (Gibb, 2015).

Entrepreneurial competences are commonly viewed as a mix of knowledge, skills and attitudes, including self-confidence, networking, and understanding risk; working with others, creativity, a sense of initiative, problem-solving, and ability to marshal resources, financial and technological knowledge (OECD, 2018; UN, 2016). The most widely used definition and model is EntreComp, the Entrepreneurship Competence Framework, developed by the European Commission as a reference guide for the twenty-eight countries of the European Union (European Commission, 2016). EntreComp offers an adaptable model that breaks entrepreneurial learning into fifteen competences across three competence areas (Figure 1), and explicitly relating these competences to life, work and business settings. This know-how model is intended to be representative of the competences for citizens that allow education systems, institutions and educators to better understand and implement the practical development of entrepreneurial competences through curricular and extracurricular learning.

Frameworks such as EntreComp provide examples of the competences that should be taught and what the associated learning outcomes could be. EntreComp offers a flexible framework that can either be adapted or copied within formal or non-formal learning settings. It identifies detailed insights into the competences and their applicability to distinct learning contexts, from life skills development to learning related to business start-ups.

Figure 1: The EntreComp Model

Source: European Commission, 2018

Education should be brought to life through practical experiential learning models and experience of real-world entrepreneurs. Gibb (2017) opines that it is important to apply the learning methods and materials associated with the real entrepreneurial environments. This observation is made because Gibb (2017) studied and compared the learning in the classroom situation and a real entrepreneur's learning environment and found that the classroom places more emphasis on the things of the past by focusing on the large amount of information, understanding, analysis and feedback. In such situation, the entrepreneur must be focused on the present and use less time for critical analysis.

Formulating proper reasoning will only occur when appropriate learning strategies are in place (Ganyanpful, 2013). The European Union report cited in Volkmann et al (2019) also concurs, noting that what students are taught and how they are taught, have implications on how best they learn. For instance, at one British University, an experiment was conducted on 114 students who enrolled for different entrepreneurship courses based on theoretical and practical learning orientation

(Piperopoulos and Dimov, 2015). The students with higher self-efficacy and theoretical lecturing orientation had higher prevention disposition toward entrepreneurial behaviour. The other group with higher self-efficacy seemed to have developed its promotion orientation for entrepreneurship. The implication is that individual entrepreneurial intention is a product of the relationship that exists between self-efficacy, self-regulation and entrepreneurial orientation in the context of adopted teaching and learning framework.

Experiential learning means learning from experience or learning by doing. Experiential education first immerses learners in an experience and then encourages reflection about the experience to develop new skills, new attitudes or new ways of thinking (Lewis and Williams, 2016). Experiential learning is aligned with the “constructivist theory of learning” in that the “outcomes of the learning process are varied and often unpredictable” and “learners play a critical role in assessing their own learning” (Wurdinger, 2015). Experiential learning can also be defined by what it is not, or how it differs from conventional academic instruction. In experiential learning, the students manages their own learning, rather than being told what to do and when to do it. The relationship between students and instructor is different, with the instructor passing much of the responsibility on to the students. The context for learning is different—learning may not take place in the classroom, and there may be no textbooks or academic texts to study. Finally, the curriculum itself may not be clearly identified—the student may have to identify the knowledge they require and then acquire it themselves, reflecting on their learning as they go along (Moon, 2018).

The model has three basic phases: an experience or problem situation; a reflective phase in which the learner examines the experience and creates learning from his/her reflection; and an application phase in which the new knowledge or skills are applied to a new problem or situation (Fig. 1)

Figure 1: Experiential Learning

Source: <https://nifa.usda.gov/sites/default/files/resource/Experiential-Learning-Model.pdf>

Experiential entrepreneurship learning is viewed not as a linear progression of knowledge acquisition, but as a complex and dynamic learning process in which the entrepreneur actively engages with the world (Pittaway and Thorpe, 2019). Learning comes from finding practical solutions to problems based on what does and does not work (Cope, 2015). Within this trial and error approach, learning is a personal journey over time (McMullen and Dimov, 2018). For this approach to be successful, the student requires a large degree of autonomy to assume personal responsibility for learning (Merriam and Bierema, 2014). Thus, experiential entrepreneurial learning requires a change in thinking from that of a passive student in a classroom to that of an active learner in control of the process. This change enables deep and meaningful learning to occur in a reflective process.

Bisk (2017) suggests mentoring as a more personalized learning process that can be a valuable tool for developing business skills of entrepreneurship. Furthermore, mentoring is a relevant concept to be used in our context because mentoring is, especially directed towards facilitation of (1) learning skills and competencies (career and behaviour related functions) and (2) the personal development and support (Kram, 2015). The mentoring interaction can facilitate a more efficient and secure transfer of complex experiences into learning (Kubberød and Jervell, 2014). Informal mentoring is more effective than formal programmes and provides some evidence that mentorship can improve self-efficacy and leadership (Sullivan, 2020). It is a two-way process in which the mentor shares his personal skills, knowledge and experience with the mentees to enable them explore their personal and professional situation, and in which the mentor and mentees work together to achieve predetermined goals and objectives. Mentoring as a function of educational institutions can be defined as a one-to-one learning relationship between an older person and a younger person that is based on modelling behaviour and extended dialogue between them (Rampton, 2015).

Broadly, security can be conceived as the absence of threats to (a) the sovereign powers and territorial integrity of a nation; (b) the capability of a country's government; (c) safety of the person and property of citizens, and (d) freedom of citizens from oppressive rule, economic exploitation, discrimination and exclusion, diseases, homelessness, starvation, ignorance and illiteracy, environmental degradation and all other forms of structural and criminal violence. Security is both a means and an end, with intrinsic value. Like every goal, the attainment of national security involves several institutional and organisational processes and activities as well as individual efforts that are governed by norms and compliance with them.

Kofi Anan (2018) stated that today we know that “security” means far more than the absence of conflict. We know that lasting peace requires a broader vision encompassing areas such as education, health, democracy and human rights, protection against environmental degradation and the proliferation of deadly weapons. We know that we cannot be secure amidst starvation, that we cannot build peace without alleviating poverty, and that we cannot build freedom on the foundations of injustice. These pillars of what we now understand as the people-centred concept of human security are interrelated and mutually reinforcing.

Statement of the Problem

The security of school has become an indispensable issue in this era of pervasive cultism. This is because schools are singled out for attack by cultists, resulting in the destruction of school plants, deaths of teaching and non-teaching staff as well as students thereby, leading to prolonged closure of schools. This development has hampered the issue of access, promoted dropout and scale down teachers’ interest in curriculum delivery. Insecurity undermines education and absence or poor quality education for citizens constitute a constraint on capacity for sustainable security in multifaceted dimensions encapsulated in human security framework. Once the security of the school is threatened, teachers become apprehensive, loss of memory sets in, resulting in the inability to deliver as effective as possible. The question now is: how can entrepreneurship curriculum be delivered in a security challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State?

Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study was to determine the entrepreneurship curriculum delivery and security challenges in Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State. Specifically, the study sought to investigate how:

- i. Experiential learning as instructional medium and entrepreneurship curriculum delivery influence security challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. Mentoring as instructional medium and entrepreneurship curriculum delivery influence security challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

These research questions guided this study:

- i. To what extent does experiential learning as instructional medium enhance entrepreneurship curriculum delivery in security challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State?
- ii. To what extent does mentoring as instructional medium influence

entrepreneurship curriculum delivery in security challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State?

Hypotheses

The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level

1. There is no significant influence of experiential learning as instructional medium on entrepreneurship curriculum delivery in security challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State.
2. There is no significant influence of mentoring as instructional medium on entrepreneurship curriculum delivery in security challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State.

Methods

The study adopted descriptive research design. The population of the study comprised 9 principals and 18 entrepreneurship teachers in the 9 public Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State. A sample size of 27 respondents was used for the study while census sampling technique was adopted. A validated 10-item instrument entitled, “Entrepreneurship Curriculum Delivery in Security Challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State Questionnaire” (ECDSCTCQ) was used for data collection. The questionnaire items were responded to on a four point scale of

Response Options	Values	Real Limit
Very much Influence (VMI)	4	3.50 – 4.00
Much Influence (MI)	3	2.50 – 3.49
Small Influence (SI)	2	1.50 – 2.49
Very Small Influence (VSI)	1	1.00 – 1.49

The Validation was done by an expert in the entrepreneurship education in the department of Business Education, University of Uyo. The reliability was established using 3 entrepreneurship teachers from Federal Girls Technical College, Uyo. The Cronbach alpha reliability method was used which yielded 0.98. The researcher with the help of seven trained research assistants, administered the questionnaires. T-test statistical analysis was used to answer research questions and test the null hypotheses at 0.05 alpha levels.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent does experiential learning as instructional medium influence Entrepreneurship Curriculum Delivery in Security Challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on Experiential learning as instructional medium and Entrepreneurship Curriculum Delivery in Security Challenged Technical Colleges N= 27

Variable	Group	N	Mean	SD	Remark
Entrepreneurship Teachers		18	40.22	18.45	Remark
Experiential learning					
Vice Principal Academic		9	29.22	8.91	VMI

VMI= Very much influence, MI = Much influence, SI=Small Influence, VSI= very small influence

Data in table 1 indicates the result of mean and standard of how experiential learning as instructional medium influences entrepreneurship curriculum delivery in security challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State, with a mean score of 40.22 for entrepreneurial teachers and 29.22 for vice principal academic. This implies that experiential learning has much influence on entrepreneurship curriculum delivery in security challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Question 2

To what extent does mentoring as instructional medium influence Entrepreneurship Curriculum Delivery in Security Challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on Mentoring as instructional medium and Entrepreneurship Curriculum Delivery in Security Challenged Technical Colleges N= 27

Variable	Group	N	Mean	SD	Remark
Experiential Teacher		18	56.56	14.70	Remark
Mentoring					
Vice principal Academic		9	41.67	22.60	VMI

Data presented in Table 2 indicates the result of mean and standard of how mentoring as instructional medium influences entrepreneurship curriculum delivery in security challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State, with a mean score of 56.56 for

experiential teacher and 41.67 for vice Principal Academic. This implies that mentoring has much influence on entrepreneurship curriculum delivery in security challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant influence of experiential learning as instructional medium on entrepreneurship curriculum delivery in security challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 3: t. Test Result on Experiential learning as instructional medium on Entrepreneurship Curriculum Delivery in Security Challenged Technical Colleges

Variable	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t-cal	Crit.-t	P-value
Experiential Learning	Experiential Teacher	18	40.22	18.45	25	7.75	2.060	.005
	Vice Principal Academic	9	29.22	8.91				

*sig @ 0.005 alpha level

Analysis shown in table 3 indicates the result of t-test on the influence of experiential learning as instructional medium on entrepreneurship curriculum delivery in security challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State, with a calculated test value of 7.75 at 25 degrees of freedom and p-value of .005. Since the p. value (.005 < .05) is less than .05, the null hypothesis is rejected. It is, therefore, concluded that there is a significant difference in responses of the principals and entrepreneurship teachers on the influence of experiential learning as instructional medium on entrepreneurship curriculum delivery in security challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant influence of mentoring as instructional medium on entrepreneurship curriculum delivery in security challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4: t. Test Result on Mentoring as instructional medium on Entrepreneurship Curriculum Delivery in Security Challenged Technical Colleges

Variable	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	t-cal	Crit.t	P-value
Mentoring	Experiential Teacher	18	56.56	14.70	25	8.18	2.060	.049
	Vice principal Academic	9	41.67	22.60				

*sig @ 0.005 alpha level

Test result in table 4 indicates the result of t-test on the influence of mentoring as instructional medium on entrepreneurship curriculum delivery in security challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State, with a calculated test value of 8.18 at 25 degrees of freedom and p-value of .049. Since the p. value ($.005 < .05$) is less than .05, the null hypothesis is rejected. It is, therefore, concluded that there is a significant difference in responses of principal and entrepreneurship teachers on the influence of mentoring as instructional medium on entrepreneurship curriculum delivery in security challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State.

Discussion of Findings

Finding of hypothesis one revealed that there is a significant influence of experiential learning as instructional medium on entrepreneurship curriculum delivery in security challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State. This is so because experiential learning, as instructional medium, involves how students manage their own learning, rather than being told what to do and when to do it. The relationship between students and instructor is different, with the instructor passing much of the responsibility on to the students. This finding supports that of Pittway and Thorpe (2019) when they opined that experiential entrepreneurship learning is not only a linear progression of knowledge acquisition, but a complex and dynamic learning process in which the entrepreneur actively engages with the world (Pittaway and Thorpe, 2019).

Hypothesis two, on the other hand, revealed that there is a significant influence of mentoring as instructional medium on entrepreneurship curriculum delivery in Security challenged Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State. This is so because mentoring is a two-way process in which the mentor shares his personal skills,

knowledge and experience with the mentees to enable them explore their personal and professional situation, while they work together to achieve predetermined goals and objectives. This finding supports the finding of Kubberød and Jervell (2014) that mentoring interaction facilitates a more efficient and secure transfer of complex experiences into learning.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that the two methods of curriculum delivery used in this study can significantly influence instructional delivery in security challenged Technical Colleges.

Recommendations

1. The Technical Board for technical education should provide security measures in Technical Colleges in the State through the provision of proper screening process during admission exercise.
2. Teachers should be adequately trained through seminars and conferences on how entrepreneurship teachers can effectively use experiential and mentoring methods for the delivery of entrepreneurship curriculum in security challenges Technical Colleges.

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